

Least squares approximation of ECG signals with rational functions

Preprocessing

Removing The Mains Frequency (50 Hz or 60 Hz). A New Method

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1. Abstract

This description is closely related to an **older article** of the same title [1]. It largely discusses the working principle of the ECG Feature Extraction (FEX) program (**progr1-123**). In the same section "4.12 Preparation", the steps of the preparatory (**prep**) program are briefly described. Between these two programs, the **oneper** program (not mentioned therein) completes the preparation process. This performs, among other things, **50 Hz band filtering** (optional) and 99 Hz low-pass filtering (also optional) of one period of the ECG signal (P, QRS, and T).

Most of the ECG equipment is mains operated, or operating near a power line. The mains frequency (British English) or by another name power line frequency (American English) in general is 50 Hz or 60 Hz. This frequency may appear in the ECG recordings, interfering with its evaluation. This should preferably be avoided, and if this fails, signal filtering is usually used. There are two types of filters, analogue and digital, and we will focus on the latter. (Although many of our findings also apply to analogue filters.)

Because of the distortion of the filters, outlined below, we have **developed a new (unknown to us so far) method to subsequently eliminate** or significantly reduce **mains noise**. In addition to the advantages of the method, there are also disadvantages and conditions, which are summarised at the end of the description of the method. We have taken an important sentence (slightly modified) from our older article [1] mentioned above:

The reason is the non-automatic generation of the ~~initial~~ parameter sets of the approximations: “view the drawing – select ~~next step~~ – mark points on the drawing”.

2. Introduction

A more detailed introduction can be found in our older article [1] mentioned above.

A few comments are made below about the 50 Hz noise filters for ECG signals. In general, when we talk about 50 Hz noise, we can also mean 60 Hz noise.

As described in Section 4.5 of [1]: “Although our method is independent of the lead system, we have mainly investigated 3 leads of the Frank system (**vx**, **vy** and **vz**; sometimes only **x**, **y** and **z**). Using Dower or inverse-Dower matrix transformations, the data of the conventional 12-lead system can be calculated from the Frank lead system data, and vice versa.”

This description assumes a basic familiarity with ECG signals, digital signal processing (including filtering) and computer programming.

3. Notes

3.1. If a filter has non-linear phase characteristics in the passband, it will cause a deformation of the signal shape, that is, this filter cannot be used for ECGs. (Although it is, possible that in some cases this distortion is not significant.)

3.2. In the ECG signal, the area around 50 Hz is still a non-negligible part! Filtering out this range causes distortion. (Although it is also possible that this distortion is not significant.) This is discussed in more detail in Section 4.

3.3. For large (e.g. national) power grids, the frequency is quite stable, with variations usually within ± 0.1 Hz.

3.4. If the mains frequency varies over time (e.g. in the case of a hospital emergency reserve aggregator), adaptive filtering can be applied.

3.5. The original Type 1 notch filter with 2 zeros has non-linear phase characteristics in the passband (and has a wide transition band). Therefore, it is of limited use for ECG signal.

3.6. In the case of linear filtering (filters are usually like this), we can check the distortion of the signal by looking at the shape of many signals that do NOT contain network noise, before and after filtering. Because the signal containing the network noise will be similarly distorted as a result of the filtering, that is, we will not get the original ECG signal back! So, if there was no network noise in the signal, the result of the filtering shows only the distortion. When testing filters, it is usually useful not only to compare the filtered signal with the original, but also to see their difference, that is, what was filtered out and whether it was really just noise.

This is also discussed in more detail in Section 4.

4. Our experience in filtering mains noise from stored digital ECG signals

4.1. Distortion caused by filtering

In this section, we will focus on only one of the two basic types of digital filters, the Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filters. Within this, the focus will mainly be on band filters since our goal is to filter out mains noise. FIR filters have linear phase characteristics in the passband, so they have the same delay at all frequencies. This delay - as is usual for stored signals - was corrected in the results of the filters.

If the result of a **band-stop filter** is subtracted from the **original signal**, a difference signal is obtained, which could have been obtained with a **band-pass filter**. *Notes:* There is a relatively simple relationship between the coefficients of these two filters: the sum of the vectors is 0 everywhere except for the middle (index = 0) coefficient, where the sum is 1, i.e. the sum is always (Dirac) $\delta(n)$. The same relationship exists between a low-pass filter and a similarly created (by extraction) high-pass filter.

Using a filter we have used so far, Figure 1a shows three curves of an ECG signal [2]: the black line is the original ECG signal, the magenta line is the signal obtained after the **band-pass filter** (NOT the other way around). Finally, the yellow line is the difference signal filtered by the 50 Hz filter, that is, the **band-pass filter** signal, moved up for better visibility.

The magnitude of the signals: See a few lines below: the so-called "small square", as well as "Data" under the latter.

Figure 1a.

The height of a “small square” is $0.1 \text{ mV} = 200 \text{ points}$. The **QRS** is ~ 10 small squares high, so $1 \text{ mV} = 2000 \text{ points}$. The **P** wave is ~ 0.5 small square high, so $0.05 \text{ mV} = 100 \text{ points}$. Finally, the **magnitude of the yellow signal** above the P wave is $\sim \pm 0.1$ small square, i.e. $\pm 0.01 \text{ mV} = \pm 20 \text{ points}$. We attached the EXCEL table based on which the plots were created {A}.

As can be seen, the original signal (black line) **does NOT contain** mains noise. However, the filtered signal contains a noise, a signal similar to 50 Hz , mainly before and after the QRS complex. So, the filtering resulted in a distortion. This was mentioned in Section 3.2: “In the ECG signal, the area around 50 Hz is still a non-negligible part!”. If this is filtered out, the signal will be distorted.

As we already mentioned in Note 3.6: “the signal **containing** mains noise will be distorted in a similar way due to the filtering”. This is because filtering **removes** the mains noise, **if any**, from the ECG, **but always** removes the segment around 50 Hz from the ECG signal spectrum. In our case: If we compare this distortion to the QRS wave of $\sim 1 \text{ mV}$, the ratio is only $\sim 1\%$ ($\pm 0.01 \text{ mV}$ and 1 mV), so it is negligible, but for the P wave this value is already $\pm 20\%$ ($\pm 0.01 \text{ mV}$

and 0.05 mV). The distortion of the ST segment is of similar magnitude (± 0.01 mV = ± 20 points).

On millimeter scale paper commonly used in ECG machines - where a 1×1 mm square (so-called "**small square**") is $40 \text{ ms} \times 200$ points (0.1 mV) - this distortion is only seen as a "thickening" of the curve, so its magnitude is negligible. However, if our goal is to process and preserve the electrical information from the heart as accurately as possible, then this can be an important difference. This $40 \text{ ms} \times 200$ points grid - enlarged according to the size of the figure - shown on all our diagrams containing ECG signals.

Data:

The ECG signal [2]: sampling rate: 1000 Hz, 1 mV corresponds to 2000 points, s0037_p008 (serial number_patient number), 10178th (10.178 sec) point of the signal is the location of the QRS signal of the period tested, vx lead.

Filter: 50 Hz \pm 1 Hz, transition bands of 1 Hz, with an accuracy of $\sim 1\%$,

GNU Octave [3], version 8.2.0, signal package: firls function, 2685 coefficients.

Figure 1a: It was created in EXCEL, just like the other large plots below.

4.2. Signal + noise filtering

The next step was to "check" the obvious correlation outlined in Section 3.6 above. Here, we examined an ECG-like signal that we constructed. **First**, the signal was filtered with the abovementioned 50 Hz filter. **Secondly**, a relatively high amplitude (0.15 mV = 300 points) "**noise**" was **added** to the original signal, and then filtering was also applied. Finally, we compared the two results. Except for calculation inaccuracies, the two signals were, as expected, identical. Since this identity is essentially based on linearity, there is no plot here, but the steps can be followed using the small Octave program attached {B}. The difference between the two abovementioned signals was a 50 Hz signal with an amplitude of ~ 1.5 points. This is an error of 0.5% (1.5 and 300), which is well within the margin of error given the 1% accuracy of the filter and the two runs.

So, of course, the filters distorted the original signal and the "noisy" signal equally. As we mentioned: "filtering **removes** the mains noise, **if any**, from the ECG, **but always** removes the segment around 50 Hz from the ECG signal spectrum". So, if this noise is removed by a filter during the pre-processing of the signals, this will cause distortion of the signal. However, as described in Section 4.1, this distortion is usually negligible under the conditions commonly used in the preparation of the ECG.

4.3. Comparison of several different filters

The plot of the filter coefficients (Fig. 1b), which is also the filter's response to a single impulse, shows that this **impulse response** contains several wave trains symmetrical to the maximum location. That is, as it moves away from the maximum location, the amplitude of the signal waves (~ 50 Hz) decreases, then goes to zero (~ 350 ms in distance), and then increases again. In addition, a 180° phase shift occurs in the zero amplitude position. The next wave train is ~ 350 ms wide.

Let's see how the difference signal mentioned in point 4.1 (the **yellow** signal in Fig. 1a) behaves symmetrically to the QRS wave, even around the much smaller P and T waves! Because its shape is very similar to the impulse response of the filter described in the previous paragraph (Fig. 1b)! That is, mainly the significant pulse of the QRS affects the filter, this results in the distortion in the sections outside the QRS wave, i.e. the P, ST, T sections. *Notes:* FIR filters are also called convolution filters. Near the large QRS wave, and **at the same time**, in the **common environment** of the (large absolute value) coefficients around the center of

the impulse response, it was expected that the results of the convolution (the signed product sums) dominate here. The presence of distortion before the QRS complex does not imply a violation of causality, because, as described in Section 4.1, the "delay - as is usual for stored signals - was corrected in the results of the filters".

So, actually, the shape of the filtered difference signal is only slightly affected by the shape of the QRS (as well as the shape of the other, smaller signals of the period). Therefore, to further investigate this type of distortion, it is sufficient to look at a signal that looks very roughly like a QRS wave. Instead of the QRS, we first examined 11 consecutive pulses of 1 mV (this is a sampled signal of a 2000 point high and 10 ms wide square pulse). Of course, this signal **does not contain any mains noise**.

Next, the effects of 3 different bandwidth filters were examined to determine how modifying the bandwidth changes the properties of the filters and in which direction.

The data of the three filters:

1. 50 Hz \pm 2 Hz, transition bands of \sim 1 Hz, with an accuracy of \sim 1%,
GNU Octave [3], signal package, firls function, 2685 coefficient.
2. 50 Hz \pm 1 Hz Identical to the filter for Figures 1a and 1b, detailed in Section 4.1.
3. 50 Hz \pm 0.1 Hz, transition bands of \sim 0.2 Hz, with an accuracy of \sim 1%,
GNU Octave [3], signal package, firls function, 14985 coefficients.

The filtering results are shown in Figures 2-7. The middle 1001 points of the **filtered difference signals** is shown in the top row (in Figures 2, 4 and 6), this is the area containing \pm 500 samples of the center of the "QRS" signal we created. This is usually approximately one period of the ECG signal (1 sec). The bottom row (Figures 3, 5 and 7) shows the full-length **filtered difference signals**. These figures show only the distortions generated outside the "QRS" signal (since the signal did not contain 50 Hz noise). Only the ratio of their magnitudes is important, knowing the effect of the Filter 2 on a real ECG signal (Fig. 1a).

At a distance of \pm 80 points from the centre of the three filters (the maximum position) (at \sim P distance from the QRS signal of real ECG signals), the "amplitudes" of the signals were measured: these were 93, 64 and 9.76 points.

Parseval's theorem predicts that if the bandwidth of the filter decreases, the amplitude of the difference signal will also decrease. Since power is directly proportional to the square of voltage, their ratio is expected to vary accordingly. Indeed, the amplitude does decrease, but this simplified calculation does not give a correct result, because the shape and length of the wave trains also change as the bandwidth changes.

Figure 2

Figure 4

Figure 6

Figure 3

Figure 5

Figure 7

Filter 3 (Figures 6 and 7) has a much smaller bandwidth and a much lower distortion of only 9.76 points. However, it can be clearly on both sides of Figure 6 that this amplitude barely decreases. So, the adjacent QRS waves will also affect the resulting distortion! Therefore, secondly, we examined the properties of several successive "QRS" signals with the Filter 3. To do this, the previous signal (which resembled a created QRS wave) was extended with four more sets of samples identical to the first. The distance between sample sets is 1000 points according to the 1000 ms time.

The **difference signal** for these 5 sample sets filtered with Filter 3 is shown in Figure 8. The amplitude of this signal at the above locations is much higher than in the previous measurement with a single sample set, that is, 28.7 points. So, the **3 amplitude values** (adjusted with the result of Filter 3) 93, 64 and 28.7 points, respectively. As we mentioned, the **ratio** of these values is important.

It can be seen that the distortion of Filter 3 is roughly half of that of Filter 2. We have also mentioned that Filter 2 is identical to the filter for Figure 1a and 1b, detailed in Section 4.1. So, if the distortion described therein at the "P wave is ... $\pm 20\%$ ", then now, for Filter 3 it will probably be only $\sim \pm 10\%$ based on proportionality. This is a more acceptable value. **However**, if a real QRS is not $\sim 1\text{mV}$ but 2 mV (and this is not even a case of „high-voltage“) and the P wave is unchanged in magnitude, then this is also $\pm 20\%$ distortion compared to this P wave, and it will be of similar magnitude in the ST segment. **Another** problem is that the **delay** for this filter is already 7.5 sec (and the same sampling duration is required after the period tested), so an ECG signal of at least 16 sec would be needed to filter the middle 1 sec period.

Finally, a Filter 4 was also examined, which is similar to Filter 3, but has a higher accuracy. Very briefly, the **accuracy** of the filters was **increased** and the width of the transition bands was reduced. This required a much larger number of coefficients, that is, **a much larger delay**, but other than that, there were no significant changes.

Note: for the 99 Hz **low-pass filter**, the distortion is much smaller at the two mentioned sections (P and S-T), approximately one-third of that shown in Figure 1a, and the distortion decreases quite rapidly away from the QRS region. We therefore consider this filter acceptable.

4.4. Conclusions

It would appear therefore that it is **difficult** to find a good **compromise** between these parameters: accuracy, bandwidth, width of transition bands, delay, and distortion. An accuracy of one thousandth requires -60 dB attenuation in the cut-off band and $\pm 0.01\text{ dB}$ ripple in the pass-band (for 1% was enough: -40 dB and $\pm 0.1\text{ dB}$).

Repeating Section 4.1: **If** we traditionally use paper where 10 mm corresponds to a 1 mV signal and the also commonly used "paper speed" of 25 mm/sec, **then** these distortions only appear as a "thickening" of the ECG curve, i.e. their magnitude is negligible. So, the 50 Hz **filters** used so far are **adequate**.

However, if we examine the ECG signals on larger images, or if our goal is to process and preserve the electrical information from the heart as accurately as possible, these distortions are already significant.

Notes:

- We have always used larger figures, here too.

- As described in Section 4.5 of [1], for the ECG data we used, the sampling frequency was 1000 Hz, and a 1 mV signal corresponded to a quantisation level of 2000 points. With newer equipment, the sampling frequency is now 4000 Hz and the vertical 1 mV signal corresponds to 25,000 points. These would already allow the ECG signal to be examined on a much larger plot.

5. A method to replace mains noise filtering of stored digital ECG signals

5.1. Method

In order to avoid the distortion of filters discussed above, we have developed a new (unknown to us so far) method to eliminate or significantly reduce mains noise. In addition to the advantages of the method, there are also disadvantages and conditions, which are summarised after the description of the method.

Very briefly: If network noise is added to the ECG signal, let's subtract this noise from the amount!

In short: in two short sections within one period (~1 sec) of the stored, noisy ECG signal, it can be approximated quite well by the sum of two functions: The first function is a polynomial of low degree (0, 1, 2) with two different parameters in the two sections. The second, **with common parameters**, is a ~50 Hz sine signal.

In more detail: looking at the curve of the signal (ECG + network noise), we look for two short sections near the beginning and end of the period, where the signal, apart from the added network noise, is approximately constant or linear or quadratic. The length of a section (for 1000 Hz sampling) should be $1+n_1*20$ points and $1+n_2*20$ points, where n_1 and n_2 are small integers. In these two short sections, this noisy signal is approximated by the method of least squares: with the two polynomials plus the **only common** ~50 Hz signal. A multiplier of 20 is appropriate because then the disturbing sine wave makes n full period. (The length of the section for 60 Hz noise is $1+n*50$.) If the frequency is slightly different from 50 Hz, this is only approximately n full periods.

The ~50 Hz signal has unknown amplitude, frequency deviation from its nominal value, and phase (**vlt1, vlt2, and vlt3**). In Fortran, for example, it might look like this:

$$\mathbf{fff} = \mathbf{vlt1} * \mathbf{DSIN}(2.0_dp * \mathbf{PI} * (50.0_dp + \mathbf{vlt2}) / 1000.0_dp * (\mathbf{ttt} + \mathbf{vlt3}))$$

Where **vlt1** is the amplitude (here it can be negative), **vlt2** is the frequency deviation from 50 Hz, and **vlt3** is the phase-related time offset. DSIN is the double-point sine function, \mathbf{ttt} is the time, 1000 is the sampling frequency, $\mathbf{PI} = \pi$ (~3.14...), and $_dp$ represents the double-point constants. If the mains is not 50 Hz, but 60 Hz, then 60 should be used in the formula.

The two polynomials have 2 to 6 parameters (depending on the number of degrees); the sine has 3 parameters, so there are 5 to 9 parameters to approximate. The approximation did not need to be broken down into sub-steps (unlike in Section 4.7 of [1]). The approximation of the **fff** function plus the two polynomials for the ECG signal with mains noise was performed in a similar way to the method described in Section 4.4 of [1]. The choice of Fortran language is justified here, and two references, [8] and [10] in [1] are linked to it.

If the approximation is considered good, the approximating sine signal is subtracted from the signal containing the mains noise, thus eliminating or significantly reducing the mains noise.

5.2. Disadvantages and conditions of the method

The main **disadvantage** of this method is that it is **not automatic**, as the signal has to be plotted (e.g. in Excel) and the two corresponding sections have to be selected from the plot. Then, some **conditions** should be checked in the plot, i.e.: whether the noise is really periodic, whether its frequency is the same as that of the mains noise, whether other noises are preferably small, and whether the mains noise characteristics are nearly constant within a period of the ECG signal (~1 sec). To judge the periodicity, it helps to draw the grid on the drawing: the vertical lines should ideally be every 20 points for a 50 Hz network (1 cycle), and every 50 points for a 60 Hz network (3 cycles), if the sampling frequency is 1000 Hz. Of course, even after the approximation, it is worth checking the plot showing the results to see if the approximation is correct.

5.3. A test

Test signal: the baseline from the original signal already shown in Figure 1a, free of mains noise, was subtracted and a 99 Hz noise filter was applied, then a ~50 Hz “noise” of medium amplitude (0.03 mV = 60 points) was **added**.

Row **a** shows the added noise data, followed by the approximation values in row **b**:

	amplitude (point),	frequency deviation,	time offset (point)
a. the mains noise we added:	60	-0.1	-6.3
b. results of the approximation:	61.22	-0.099	-6.41

In Figure 9, the "sign to app" that needs to be approached. The "polynomial" is part of the approximation with two first-degree polynomials. While "sin" is the sine part of the result of the two approximations, it is plotted over the entire signal section.

In Figure 10, “orig” is the original signal (subtracting only the baseline), “appx” is the approximate signal (without the 99 Hz filtering), and “delta” is the difference between the previous signals, i.e. the **error**. The maximum error is ± 2.55 points.

In both figures, the peaks of the QRS waves were cut (only in the figure) because they did not contain any extra information that would have been visible to the eye and would have only increased the height of the figure. The size of the orange “delta” signal is still barely visible. For the purposes of completeness, we also include the source data {C} for this figure.

Continue on the next page!

Figure 9

Figure 10

5.4. A real-world task

Below are two plots of a **real-world** task. In the two figures (Figures 11 and 12), the **vy** lead of the same ECG signal is the baseline signal. This already includes 50 Hz mains noise. In the figures, the signs are named as in Figures 9 and 10 (of course, “delta” is missing). In this case, it was not necessary to cut off the QRS peaks. However, it is striking that the positive peaks of the QRS in Figures 11 and 12 are differently shaped, which is a consequence of using 99 Hz filtering (the very narrow central peak was eliminated by the filtering). Also **included** are the data for the plots {D} and the **source code for the Fortran program that performs the approximation** {E}.

Figure 11

Figure 12

5.5. Conclusions

As described in Section 5.2: “The main **disadvantage** of this method is that it is **not automatic**, as the signal has to be plotted (e.g. in Excel) and the two corresponding sections have to be selected from the plot”.

Choosing the sections is usually not a problem: often the T wave of the previous period has already ended before the P wave and there is a zero signal, or if there is no end, the end of the T wave can be approximated by a straight. The other possibility is the peak of the T wave, which can usually be approximated by a quadratic polynomial.

Conditions:

If the mains noise is not periodic, then of course the method is not applicable (but neither is filtering).

If the period does not match that of the mains, then its frequency must be determined approximately and the 50 constant of the frequency should be replaced in the **fff** function.

If other noises are significant, it is worth filtering them out first, perhaps using the 99 Hz filter.

The 3 parameters of the mains noise usually do not change in ~1 sec. If they do (for example, a high-current device is switched off or on), one can try processing another period.

Results:

If the approximation is deemed inadequate, another section has to be selected. At which of the two sections, it becomes clear from the shape of the polynomials of the approximation. If that is no good either, another period can be selected.

The advantages:

The method is basically fast, no filters are needed, and there is no “distortion”. In addition, one period of the signal will suffice (since there is no delay, see Section 4.3).

6. Annexes

{A} for Section 4.1	Figure 1a	sam-oneper_2.xls	
{B} for Section 4.2		torzit_50Hz.m,	39_filter_49_51_firls_4.txt
{C} for Section 5.3	Figures 9, 10	t2rajz50Hz_2.txt	
{D} for Section 5.4	Figures 11, 12	rajz50Hz-y.txt	
{E} for Section 5		de50Hz-u-111-z_123.f95	fcn_6.f95 progr1-50Hz-z_123.bat sam-oneper.txt

6. References

- [1] <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7628747>
- [2] Goldberger AL, Amaral LAN, Glass L, Hausdorff JM, Ivanov PCh, Mark RG, et al. "PhysioBank, PhysioToolkit, and PhysioNet: Components of a New Research Resource for Complex Physiologic Signals" *Circulation* 101(23):e215-e220 [Circulation Electronic Pages; <http://circ.ahajournals.org/cgi/content/full/101/23/e215>]; 2000 (June 13). PMID: 10851218; doi: 10.1161/01.CIR.101.23.e215
- [3] John W. Eaton, David Bateman, Søren Hauberg, Rik Wehbring (2023).